

Perceived Urgency of Vibrotactile Patterns on the Back

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Abstract. This study compares perceived urgency and discernability of vibrotactile patterns on the back across three motor activation modes (slow sequential, fast sequential, simultaneous), with and without cognitive load. Results show that slow activation yields higher perceived urgency compared to fast activation, while both yield higher pattern recognition rates than simultaneous activation.

Keywords: Vibrotactile Alerts, Cognitive Load, Pattern Recognition

1 Introduction

Vibrotactile alerts can support emergency responders such as firefighters when vision and audio are obstructed. These alerts will often be used under high cognitive load, yet it is unclear how this affects the perceived urgency [1]. For auditory alerts, perceived urgency increases with rate of change [2], whereas for vibrotactile alerts urgency increases with duration within the first 400 ms [3]. Since a slower rate of change leads to a longer duration, it is unclear how this will affect the perceived urgency of vibrotactile alerts. We compared perceived urgency and identification rates for three vibrotactile activation modes induced on the back, with and without cognitive load.

2 Method

The study was approved by the ERB of the HTI group at Eindhoven University of Technology. 15 participants (7 male; 8 female; aged 18-24 years) took part in the study. Participants were naive to the experiment purpose and received € 9,- (university students) or € 12,- (others). They rated the perceived urgency of vibrotactile patterns delivered using 20 motors (5 rows × 4 columns, spacing 7 and 8 cm, respectively) on the back of a vibrotactile vest (bHaptics Tactsuit X40 [4]). Urgency was defined as “*the quality of being very important and needing immediate attention*” and rated using free magnitude estimation. We manipulated the activation mode of the vibrotactile patterns (Slow, Fast, Simultaneous) and the presence of a visual search (VS) task [5]. Six vibrotactile patterns (Fig. 1) representing generic shapes were used. In the Simultaneous activation, the motors were activated for 1.5 seconds. In the Fast and Slow activation modes, motors were activated sequentially over 1 second or 2 seconds, respectively. Trials were blocked by VS condition and activation mode, counterbalanced across participants. Each of the 6 blocks contained all 6 patterns and one repetition.

Participants wore the vibrotactile vest and were seated in front of a computer screen. They first completed 10 practice trials. A frame in the VS condition lasted 2 seconds and had a 50% chance of containing a target (red ‘T’) among 19 distractors (blue ‘T’ or inverted red ‘T’), or only 20 distractors. Participants pressed the space bar upon detecting the target. After 2-8 frames (randomly selected to prevent participant from anticipating the end) the VS task ended and a vibrotactile pattern was activated. Participants rated the urgency of the pattern on a free magnitude scale and selected which of the 6 patterns (represented in a diagram) they perceived. Without the VS, the same rating and identification display appeared after every vibrotactile activation.

Perceived urgency was analyzed using a linear mixed model (LMM) and pattern recognition using a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) with a binomial link function. Predictors were activation mode, presence of a VS task, and their interaction. Type-III Analyses of Variance (ANOVA) of the models are reported and assumptions were met.

3 Results

Fig. 1. Left: The six vibrotactile patterns (circles represent motors). In sequential stimulation, activation starts at dark blue motors, follows the arrows, and ends at the small circles. Numbers indicate activation timesteps; motors sharing a number were activated simultaneously. Right: Boxplots of perceived urgency (z-scores) by activation mode and VS presence. Whiskers denote $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$; points indicate outliers. Brackets mark significant differences.

The VS task correct rate was well above chance ($M = 94.8 \pm 3.3\%$; $\text{min} = 87.5\%$). Fast activation was rated lowest on perceived urgency, while Simultaneous activation rated highest (Fig. 1). The effect of activation mode was significant ($F_{2, 84} = 195.37$, $p < 0.001$). Contrast analyses revealed Slow was rated significantly more urgent than Fast ($t \text{ ratio} = 7.94$, $p < 0.001$), and Simultaneous activation was rated more urgent than both Slow ($t \text{ ratio} = -18.28$, $p < 0.001$) and Fast ($t \text{ ratio} = -26.22$, $p < 0.001$).

Pattern identification rate was higher with Slow (95% no-VS; 93% VS) and Fast activation (93% no-VS; 87% VS) than with Simultaneous activation (44% no-VS;

43% VS). The effect of activation mode was significant ($\chi^2(2) = 122.42, p < 0.001$). Contrast analyses showed higher identification rates with Slow (z ratio = 12.10, $p < 0.001$), and Fast (z ratio = 11.70, $p < 0.001$) activation compared to Simultaneous.

4 Discussion

Slow sequential vibrotactile pattern activation was perceived as more urgent than Fast activation. This is in contrast to auditory alerts, for which a higher rate of change increases perceived urgency [2]. This effect may result from the longer total duration of Slow activation, suggesting that the urgency plateau after 400 ms reported for localized vibrotactile stimuli [3] does not generalize to sequential patterns distributed over larger body areas, such as the back. The presence of a visual search task did not have a significant effect on perceived urgency or pattern identification. This is similar to [1], where the effect of a memorization task was unclear. In both cases, the cognitive load may have been insufficient to influence vibrotactile perception.

4.1 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Our preliminary work on vibrotactile alerts for emergency responders provides insights into how activation speed influences urgency perception. Open questions remain on the role of cognitive load, as we found no effect when induced through a visual search task, but field operators likely experience higher workloads. We invite human factor researchers to discuss varied ways to induce and isolate effects of cognitive load.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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